

Sales & Marketing Management Trends In 2025; Tracking and Measuring Sales Performance

Author: Seyed Farzad Mirmiran¹, Business & Academic
Researcher, CEU university;
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14434188

Summary

Tracking and measuring sales performance is crucial for optimizing sales efforts and driving business growth. CEOs must understand the value of sales metrics and embrace data-driven decisions to refine strategies and improve results. Clear and concise business writing is vital when preparing reports that present key sales data, trends, and insights in an actionable way. This article explores how CEOs can leverage sales metrics, the importance of measuring performance, and how clear reporting can help refine strategies, enhance sales effectiveness, and contribute to faster growth.

1 - Senior Academic & Business Researcher at
CEU University;

[\(Dr.Seyed Farzad Mirmiran \(gumroad.com\) or;](https://www.gumroad.com/dr/mirmiran)
<https://drmirmiran.gumroad.com/> &
drmirmiran@yahoo.com)